

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

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Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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D7.3: Dissemination and Communication Plan Final

Public Executive Summary

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Executive Summary

This document presents the final Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) for the OXIPRO project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 101000607). Spanning from June 2020 to May 2025, OXIPRO has developed innovative enzyme-based solutions to drive the transition towards environmentally friendly consumer products across key industrial sectors, including detergents, cosmetics, textiles, and nutraceuticals.

The Communication and Dissemination strategy was designed from the outset to ensure that OXIPRO's objectives, outputs, and impacts were effectively promoted to a diverse range of stakeholders. This has been achieved through a robust combination of scientific dissemination, industry outreach, citizen engagement, and policy advocacy — in full compliance with Articles 29 and 38 of the Grant Agreement. The CDP has evolved through successive versions (Deliverables D7.1 and D7.2), reflecting OXIPRO's progress, emerging opportunities, and stakeholder feedback.

Throughout its four-year lifetime, OXIPRO implemented a dynamic, multi-channel communication approach, including a dedicated project website, active social media presence, newsletters, scientific publications, stakeholder workshops, policy briefs, and public engagement campaigns. Special emphasis was placed on open access, ensuring that all peer-reviewed publications and major deliverables are freely available via platforms such as Zenodo.

By the project's conclusion, OXIPRO has:

- Surpassed its scientific dissemination targets, achieving more than 10 open-access publications (Deliverable D7.6);
- Expanded its stakeholder database to over 800 contacts (partially covered in Deliverable D1.1 and Deliverable D1.3);
- Participated in high-impact European conferences and international workshops, and sector-focused or industry events.
- Released three policy briefs advocating for the integration of enzyme technologies under Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSBD) frameworks (partially covered in Deliverable D1.4);
- Delivered targeted communication activities to citizens, particularly younger audiences, through three innovative awareness-raising campaigns (Deliverable D7.7).

The final CDP not only captures the full range of activities and outputs but also sets a clear pathway for sustaining OXIPRO's legacy. Continued access to project materials, scientific findings, and collaboration networks will ensure that the innovations developed during the project continue to influence research, industry, and policy development well beyond the project's formal end.

OXIPRO's commitment to open innovation, stakeholder engagement, and sustainability has positioned it as a reference initiative in the advancement of greener, enzyme-enabled technologies for Europe's bioeconomy and circular economy transition.